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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

JESSALYN M. ANSALE

Teacher I
Sanyata Elementary School
jessalyn.ansale@deped.gov.ph

CJAY G. MISAGAL

Teacher I
Sanyata Elementary School
cjay.misagal@deped.gov.ph

ANGEL JOY G. VILLACORTA

Teacher I
Maglambing Integrated School
angeljoy.villacorta@deped.gov.ph

IVY L. APALACIO

Teacher I
Mahaba Elementary School
ivyapalacio19@gmail.com

RACQUEL S. LAWANGON

lawangonracquel@gmail.com

RN R. GENOTIVA

Teacher III
Wakat Elementary School
rn.raza@deped.gov.ph

ALLAN B. GEMAO

Teacher I
Mantuyom Elementary School
allan.gemao@deped.gov.ph

JIRAH B. GEMAO

Volunteer Teacher
Mantuyom Elementary School
jhaijhai435@gmail.com

RODELYN O. PERALES

Volunteer Teacher
Mantuyom Elementary School
rodelynperales94@gmail.com

DR. RIO S. CONSIGNA-ADORABLE

Dean, College of Teacher Education
Andres Soriano Colleges of Bislig
rioconsign82@gmail.com

“TEACHING AND TEACHER EDUCATION”

Teaching as a profession is what most teachers consider it, as a passion and it is a public notion that they took up education in college in order to become a teacher. The truth is, there are teachers who are education unit earner in the teaching profession. It is believed to be, that teaching is one's destiny because a teacher is more than a student, and who in the earth would like to be a student until its retirement. Teaching as a career and your employment could be a calling rather than a profession. A teacher is born with a mission and with a heart of understanding and passion because one can never succeed without these basic qualities of a teacher. It is never in a wildest dream on some of the teachers that they want to be a teacher, because

everybody wants to finish schooling since getting into school every day is a tiring job. Everybody has a dream but no man in this world has the total control of what would be their lives in the coming years.

A teacher starts upon assumption of its first day of duty and that is, after taking its oath of office. Once a teacher enters the school's gate, he or she must have to wear its Department of Education's prescribed school's uniform for public school teachers with its identification card hanging on its neck; and he or she is required to discharge its duties and functions as required by existing rules and regulations of the Civil Service Commission whose mandate is to implement laws to all government officials and employees in relation to their job. A particular teacher has its own master teacher under the supervisory also of its school's principal. Elementary to Junior High School has its own schedule of classes every year, except to the Senior High School with two semesters in one school year, hence, teacher has its schedule every semester.

Normally under the CSC all government employees must render eight hours in a day including also the teachers; and its school time starts at 8:00 in the morning and it ends at 4:00 in the afternoon. While big school has flexible time depending on its teacher's schedule. So that a teacher, his service ends after eight hours unless of some exigencies of the service as required by the office. A teacher attends seminar and training for professional growth as required by RA 6713 otherwise known as the "Code of Ethics for Public Officials and Employees" including all public-school teachers. A teacher also needs to attend in-service training in the school where a teacher belongs, through its Master teacher as immediate supervisor; basically, to enhance and update its method of teaching and should also engaged in action research in order to come-up findings and as basis to design innovation and strategies.

Teacher education could be true as the noblest profession and it is the highest profession to be accorded with highest honor and respect more than a barangay captain or a president of certain country for that matter, because all professions start from teacher education. Before, those who enrolled education is believed to be not so much intelligent; this time, teacher education as a chosen career must be at least bright or intelligent since the standards and the examination that is being set by the Professional Regulation Commission in taking the Licensure Examination for Teachers is quite difficult. However, anybody can still be a teacher for as long as one has a passion of teaching and still could be a good teacher.

Teaching nowadays using the Most Essential Learning Competencies on the K to12 Curriculum guide is student-centered learning, employment or job oriented, has the option of online and distance learning, more personalized learning with more weight on performance task of the learners. Traditional teachers who are used of traditional methods of teaching such as lecture method give full lecture on the lesson or topic, unlike today that teacher only facilitate and guide learners. However, for the millennial teachers are more comfortable since they were born when the use of technology is popular.

The Issues therefore in teaching lie on the quality of teaching. If the k12 program using the MELCS meets the demand of the market in preparing the learners for employment, therefore the gap of employment is reduced. In the actual scenario, unemployment increases that it may be explained the Philippine's result on basic education international standard aptitude test such as the PISA where the Philippine is lagged behind from other countries. Basic education is accessible and free, being guaranteed under the 1987 Philippine Constitution yet, it has high dropped- out among the vulnerable sector of this country. There could have a lot of issues that the government must address to improve the educational system including poverty, limited and outdated textbooks including the ratio of the students and teachers is high which finds it difficult to the teacher to give individual attention to every learner. Challenges also which should be addressed by the Department of Education is more on how to develop standardized test align to the international standard test so that

learner's academic performance is achieved. This is a national concern that needs immediate intervention by creating methodologies and approaches in monitoring and evaluating the educational system of the country.

The general behavior of a teacher as far as knowledge and affective skills is concerned has a relationship to teacher education. It refers to the educational institution that provides the programs regulated by the Commission on Higher Education. The teacher acquires principles, theories and its practice on its teaching career, however, there are teachers' behavior which are not taught in their formative years while in college, these are only developed while they are teaching. Therefore, teaching and learning is a continuous process, and a teacher acquire unique personality while teaching. Generally speaking, teachers connect students to unknown possibilities. They introduce learners to the world by honing their skills and talents. In the process, the learners become a friend of the teacher who treated them just like their sons and daughters. But what makes unique, there are various types of teachers that learners maybe unaware of it, that it affects the teaching process of a certain teacher. Learners could not just predict their teachers whether a learner could pass on the subject of that certain teacher, the reason why there are learners who are very anxious and conscious of their grades. A teacher who requires a student to explain why the latter is unable to take the examination or comply its requirements; there are teachers that upon looking its physical structures the learners are afraid of; teachers without any reasons that they are very strict; a teachers will cry when gets angry inside the classroom; teachers who are boring, teachers who are like and action a star or a dramatic teacher also. These are just but few of the unique characteristics of a teachers that has impacted to the learning and behavior of the learner. Therefore, maybe, the notion that there are no good students only good teacher in some aspect is true, and it is always true that the future of one's nation depends on what types of teachers do we have in our country and it is maybe related to teacher education.

In the final analysis, Teaching career is like farming. The teacher planted good seeds in a vast fertile land. These good seeds are values and positive behavior embedded on the lessons presented by the teacher. These seeds grow very fast when it is nurtured and cared by the teacher. Just like a growing plant when it is watered every day, it bears fruit abundantly, like a teacher who always reminds student on proper attitude and values and how to behave properly in accordance to the standard ethics of the society. In order a plant to grow very healthy, it needs some natural approach so that its development is rooted from its natural capacity, just like a learner, who develops his talents and skills in a natural way also. It could have maybe some hereditary factors that contributes to the success of a certain learner. The teacher education is the open field where a plant starts to grow. The knowledge that a teacher acquires in that open field is transfer to other portion of the soil, the vast land where it grows independently with the guidance of the farmer who are the teacher in that particular school. To capture a beautiful picture of one's teaching life is reflected on the camera to the learners. The general lens is the government that provides and supports the needs of the program of the Department of Education to attain its goals and objectives. What could be actually true in the lower level would radiate upwards and vice versa. Therefore, to strongly build one's nation is to create and develop good teacher and build a responsive teacher education. When a government invest on education, we build a brighter future of the nation.